

A Comparative Analysis of Husband and Wife Relationships from Confucian and Buddhist Perspectives

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Abstract: Equal rights and obligations should be shared by spouses when it comes to running the home. Confucian and Buddhist philosophies emphasize the importance of social relationships in creating a peaceful society. To create a happy and peaceful marriage, a comparative analysis of the husband and wife relationship was done in this study. This paper compares and contrasts the relationship between husband and wife from the Buddhist and Confucian perspectives. An analytical descriptive method was used to get the findings of the study. This study surveys two philosophies: the teachings of the Buddha and Confucius which focus on the duties of husband and wife. Data were collected from various sources of both literatures. The study found similarities between the two literatures, according to which the wife runs the home and raises the children and the husband takes the lead. However, because of the different cultures and customs, both view points offer distinct guidelines for creating a long-lasting marriage. Confucian philosophy accepts the practice of having a second wife for the continuation of family lineage whereas in Buddhist philosophy, a wife is not responsible for that. In conclusion, the study found that the Buddhist and Confucian perspectives on the husband-wife relationship have similarities and differences.

Keywords: A Comparative analysis , husband and wife, similarities, differences

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Introduction

The foundation of a civilization is built upon a network of interdependent and mutually entwined ties. In a group or community, every relationship represents an unwavering commitment to upholding and defending others. Marriage plays a vital role in this strong network of relationships that provides security and support. A healthy marriage should gradually emerge from understanding rather than impulse, and from genuine loyalty rather than merely indulgence.

Many people believe that marriage is an important and necessary event in life. However, in order to have a successful marriage, couples should try to minimize their differences and learn to synchronize their lives. Unfortunately,

some marriages may face issues and conflicts. In fact, there is a saying that a blind wife and a deaf husband would have a peaceful marriage because the blind wife cannot notice her husband's flaws, and the deaf husband cannot hear his wife's complaints. (Dr. K. SriDhammananda,1995)

The majority of Chinese couples are found to be happy in their married lives, but there is disagreement over what constitutes a good marriage. Like people in other cultures, Chinese women are expected to work outside the home and also to be "good wives and loving mothers." (Xuewen,2004,p.108-110) Chinese men are expected to earn more money and be the main breadwinners. Therefore, it is essential for the husband and wife to understand, care for, and adjust to one another to have a happy marriage.

Improving compassion and understanding between spouses can be achieved through effective communication. Spending quality time together, discussing matters frequently, showing consideration towards one another's emotions, and similar actions can all contribute to achieving this goal. Additionally, arrangements such as dividing household chores and working towards a more equal power dynamic can exhibit mutual understanding and compassion. In Chinese culture, it is common for spouses to give their wives some control over domestic tasks and decision-making authority.

This study aims to gain a deeper understanding of the interactions between married couples in two different societies with opposing beliefs and values: Buddhist and Confucian societies. The ultimate goal is to contribute to the development of successful and fulfilling marriages. By examining these contrasting perspectives on marriage, it is hoped that the research will help to maintain happy, peaceful relationships between spouses.

The Relationship between Husband and Wife in Buddhism

The duties of being a husband and wife go beyond those of being parents in a family. Married life is not an easy one as it requires the merging of two people with totally different background, attitudes and lifestyles. Only the love that a husband and wife share can fulfill the gaps between them. Apart from love, duties, and responsibilities play an important role in family life. The duties of both husbands and wives as the Buddha taught can be described as follows. The husband's five responsibilities include tending to the wife as follows:

- 1 By treating her with respect.
- 2 By not showing her discourtesy.
- 3 By not being unfaithful to her.
- 4 By handing over authority to her.
- 5 By providing her with adornments. (Digha Nikāya,1954,p.39)

By fulfilling and upholding his marital duties to his spouse, a husband can demonstrate his faithfulness to her and uphold her confidence in the marriage in all senses of the word. Taking the lead role in the family, the husband should delegate domestic responsibilities to the wife, who should be viewed as the home's economic administrator, as he would often stay away from home.

The husband must compliment his wife and be understanding of her faults rather than using abusive language, placing blame on her, or making her feel inferior. He ought to offer his wife his earnings. He shouldn't act inappropriately. He ought to cherish his wife, be devoted to her, and give her ornaments. They will have mutual affection if he understands his obligations and makes an effort to fulfill them, and their union will be harmonious.

The main reasons for marital issues are mistrust and suspicion. Many people view marriage as a curse due to ignorance, even though it is a blessing.

It is important for husband and wife to have implicit trust in one another and to avoid keeping secrets from one another. Hidden information breeds distrust, which in turn breeds jealousy, which in turn breeds rage, which breeds hostility, which can lead to divorce, suicide, or even murder. (Dr. K. SriDhammananda,1995)

A couple who share both happiness and sorrow can comfort one another and reduce their complaints in daily life. Therefore, it is important not to expect only good times but also to be prepared to endure unpleasant and painful events. They need to have a strong determination to overcome difficulties and misunderstandings. Discussing their common interests can help them to coexist more understandingly.

Both men and women need support from each other during difficult times. If someone is willing to share the burden, feelings of uneasiness and unhappiness can disappear, making life more meaningful, joyful, and exciting.

On the other hand, the wife, having been ministered thus by the husband in these five duties:

1. She manages her work very well.
2. She looks after the household stores and property.
3. She is not unfaithful to him.
4. She is hospitable to those around her such as servants and husband's relatives.
5. She is skillful and diligent in all her duties. (Buddhaghosa, Ashin, 1960, p.48)

It is crucial to remember that a woman is a partner of equal standing in a fulfilling partnership that should be fostered by both sides, not only a natural or feminine gift to her husband. A wife ought to be treated with genuine loyalty, gentleness, and committed dedication to her husband, as per the list of tasks she is supposed to fulfill his demands.

If a wife is competent and ethical, she is capable of managing and distributing assets that belong to the marriage. It is also important that both sides' parents receive equal support. By fulfilling her responsibilities, a wife can foster love and happiness in the marriage.

In describing fourth duty in his book, Dr. K. Sri Dhammananda shares advices given by the Buddha to young women before their marriage. (Dr. K. Sri Dhammananda, 1995) They were instructed to treat their mothers-in-law and fathers-in-law with utmost respect, treating them as if they were their parents. The Buddha also emphasized the importance of treating their husbands' friends and family with dignity and respect. This was to ensure that their new homes would be welcoming and joyful, despite any potential challenges that may arise.

The guidance of the Buddha from over 25 centuries ago remains relevant in modern times. Women were advised to understand their husbands' personalities, behaviors, and dispositions, and to be helpful and cooperative in their new homes. They were also encouraged to be considerate, courteous, and cautious with their husband's money, and to ensure that all home expenses were managed correctly.

The third duty of husband and wife was described as follows. When people are in love, they tend to show only their best qualities to each other. They do this to maintain a positive image of themselves. However, this means that they may fail to see the worst aspects of each other's personalities. Both lovers will try to present only their admirable traits to the other, and because they are so deeply in love, they may take each other at face value alone. Each lover will keep their darker side hidden, out of fear of losing the other. When two people are interested in each other, they may try to hide any personal flaws or shortcomings in order to increase their chances of winning the other person's heart. If someone falls in love, they may also overlook their partner's flaws, believing that their love is strong enough to overcome any challenges and that they can work together to fix any issues that arise.

But after marriage, when the honeymoon phase fades, each partner's actual personality will come to light. Then, to the great dismay of both sides, the metaphorical curtain that had been hiding each partner's deepest emotions is lifted to reveal their actual selves. That's when the disillusionment starts.

In modern times, numerous families have been broken due to various reasons such as the wife's inability to manage the household effectively, her negative attitude towards her husband's relatives and friends, her disloyalty, and her extravagant spending habits that drain the husband's hard-earned savings. Therefore, it is crucial that we adhere to the Buddha's teachings and guidelines for both husbands and wives. By doing so, we can uphold and appreciate the importance of healthy, happy, and ethical family relationships.

According to Sumedho, a wife is worthy of a husband's praise and assured of her identity as a wife; he should not look down on her; he should not be unfaithful; he should give her a chance to manage the household, family, and finance; and he should give her trinkets and ornaments. In return, a woman should effectively manage the household, encourage her husband's family and friends to avoid adultery, take care of the family's properties, and work hard. (Sumedho, 1995, p.169)

Furthermore, Payutto Bhikkhu (Payutto Bhikkhu, 1998, p.55) suggests a virtue of couple sharing in goodness, there are four principles for household life, known as the *gharāvāsadhamma* as follows:

1. Truthfulness (*sacca*); being truthful and faithful to each other in thoughts, speech and, deeds.
2. Training (*dama*); exercising restraint, training themselves to correct faults, resolve differences, adapt to each other, and improve themselves.
3. Patience (*khanti*); being firm, stable and patient; not reacting impulsively to each other's affronts; enduring difficulties and hardships and overcoming obstacles together.
4. Sacrifice (*caga*); being thoughtful, able to give up personal comfort for the sake of one's partner by, for example, foregoing sleep in order to nurse him or her in sickness; also being kind and generous, not uncharitable, to the relatives and friends of one's partner. (Saṃyutta Nikāya Pāḷi, 1960, p.215)

The husband and wife should work together to find solutions to problems in their relationship, while always treating each other with respect. They should also take care of each other when one is sick and help their less fortunate friends.

According to *Aṅguttara*, a marriage is not the belonging of only one spouse; it must be constituted as a whole by both wife and husband. Each person has their own duties to perform according to their different roles. A couple can build a loving family based on love applying the virtues mentioned above. Only with the compatible faith, moral conduct, generosity and wisdom of the couple, a strong family life will be built. (Aṅguttara Pāḷi, Vol II, 2007, p.60)

According to Peter Harvey, if husband and wife are matched in faith, moral conduct, generosity and wisdom, they will be reborn together in the next life if they wish so. Although Buddhism does not object to divorce, it is not common among Buddhist society as societal factors prevent it from being frequent practice. In contrast to certain societies, single women are respected in Buddhist ethics. Laws relating to divorce, the division of property, and children are equal for both husband and wife. (Peter Harvey, 2013, p.15)

The Relationship between Husband and Wife in Confucianism

Confucianism considers the relationship between husband and wife to be secondary to other family relationships, such as those between a father and son or between elder and younger brothers. However, marriage holds great significance for Confucians, both within the family and in society as a whole. The Book of Rites, a classic Confucian text, describes marriage as "the union of two surnames through friendship and love". (Li Chi, 1885) From a family perspective, marriage can bring together families with different surnames (clans) and continue the family legacy of those clans. Therefore, the benefits and drawbacks of the clans, rather than the individual couple, are the primary concern in marriage.

Confucianism's teaching, though brief, is unmistakable:

"In the sky, there are not two suns, nor in a land, not two kings, nor in a state, not two rulers, nor in a family, not two equally honorable: one principle regulates all these conditions."
Thus, it is stated, while the wife's period of mourning for her husband was of the highest degree, lasting three years, her husband's period of mourning for her was only of the second degree, lasting only one year, "showing that there are not in the family two equally honorable." (Li Chi, 1885, p.28)

The above description of a Confucian as the husband in the family is like the sun in the sky so the wife is like the earth. The way of the earth, the way of a bride, the way of a minister is that if the inferior is successful, he will not claim that success for himself. This is the way of the earth to carry things to their rightful conclusion rather than claiming the merit of accomplishment.

According to the dualistic theory of '*yin yang*', which was already discussed, husband and wife are thus associated as the sun and the earth, with '*yang*,' the masculine principle, being personified by the sun and '*yin*,' the feminine principle, by the earth. (Hsu, 1932, p.6-70)

He is the '*chia chang*,' the master of the house, and Chinese wives commonly refer to their husbands as the '*tang chia ti*,' the person who serves as the family's head and head of the home. (Mateer, 1900, p.94) When the husband sings, the woman joins in the chorus, or as the saying puts it: "When the husband sings, the wife joins in the chorus," there will be "harmony between husband and wife," (Macleod, 1938, p.185) which the Classics believe should define the marital partnership.

According to Smith, "Harmonious, united below the husband sings, the wife accompanies." (Smith, 1902, p.41)

In Confucianism, there is a practice of separating young men and women. The decision to marry was solely in the hands of the parents. Once a girl became a wife, she had greater responsibilities, including satisfying her husband's desires and bearing a son to carry on the family name. Additionally, she was expected to please her husband's family, especially her mother-in-law. (Li, 2000, p.1-21)

Wives: Women were expected to adhere to "the three obediences and the four virtues." The three obediences require women to obey their father before marriage, their husband during marriage, and their sons if they become widows. (Cheng, 2008, p.15-37)

Pan Zhao, a passionate follower of Confucius and the daughter of a well-known scholar, strongly supported the four virtues and the three obediences. She argues in her book *Precepts for Women* that a woman should be respected for being like a shadow and an echo rather than for being attractive, smart, or talkative. (Gao, 2003, p. 114-125) It is evident that the "three obediences and the four virtues" function in concert to give men advantages in the social, political, and economic spheres that are unavailable to women.

Wives are often expected to take care of the home, and children, and stay at home. However, this can lead to social isolation.

The Four Virtues and the Three Obediences, or Submissions, comprise the Confucian moral precept. The Three Obediences state that a woman should be obedient to her husband in marriage, to her father and elder brothers when she is a young woman, and to her son when she is a widow in an effort to provide stricture to every aspect of a woman's life. In contrast, the Four Virtues give propriety norms that enable a woman to control her life and behavior. The first virtue is a woman's capacity to recognize, respect, and adjust her behavior to fit into a subservient role in society. Restraining speech is the second virtue, as talkative women are viewed as being both annoying and unfriendly. The third virtue advises a woman to beautify and dress herself to appeal to men. The final virtue demands that a woman be able to manage her home properly and perform all household chores with joy.

Husband-Chinese husbands are distant from their wives if they are constantly around other people, even at home among family and friends, in addition to never being seen together in public. (Smith, 1899, p. 302-303)

He moves ahead of her in public and leaves her hidden to follow behind when they pass through doors, which is in sharp contrast to his remarkable kindness to a fellow human being. In contrast to being her husband's buddy, she is seen as inferior and serves her spouse. It's doubtful that his attacking her would inspire love. In contrast, Macleod cited that "it must not be assumed that Chinese husbands do not love their wives because they beat them, for that is not the case." (Macleod, 1938, p.187)

If a wife is ill, and the males of the family treat her with utter callousness and indifference, it is another sign that they don't value her. She is allowed to keep on hurting while rejecting medical care. (Macleod, 1938, p.187)

Marriage Life: She has, at best, a secondary place in her husband's thoughts and considerations since, as a responsible son, he always puts his parents' interests before those of his wife. The proverb states that "He is an undutiful son who loves his wife and disobeys his mother." (Plopper, 1926,p.89)

In a disagreement, the Chinese partner will nearly always support his mother instead of his wife. Men are frequently advised not to listen to "the slanders" of their spouses. (Macleod, 1938,p. 188.)

Lee claims that "the Chinese say everything depends on the son and the husband; if he is faithful to his parents and strict in maintaining family discipline, he can prevent domestic disputes; if he only shuts his ear to his wife's complaints, peace will be preserved." (Lee, 1887, p. 31-32.)

As Mencius (372-289 BC) stated, not having children is seen as the most unfilial act. In the past, a woman's worth was often judged based on her ability to bear a son. Even if she excelled in other aspects of life, failure to continue the family name through a male heir could result in her losing favor and being humiliated. (Tang, 1995,p. 269–84.) This could lead to her being discarded or sold into prostitution or servitude to wealthy families. It was generally considered a virtue for a wife to find a secondary wife (妾, qie) for her husband. Such practices were unfair and degrading to women.

In ancient China, a secondary wife was a female spouse with legal recognition but held a lower position in the marriage compared to the main wife. (Li, 2000,p 1–21).Husbands often marry secondary wives due to their tendency to change their minds and their main wives' inability to conceive. When a wife gave birth to multiple boys, her status in the family was elevated, even though she still had a subordinate role and was not responsible for disciplining her son. In some cases, a wife could only tell her son that she would complain to his father, as that was the extent of her power.

Marriage has caused these two people to become close. Since society expects the husband to wed the wife, making the husband the superior party, the woman is the inferior partner in this partnership. The husband is essential in standing up for and protecting his wife. On the other hand, the woman takes on the duty of taking care of her husband by being obedient to her spouse. Confucius noted, however, that in order for this relationship to succeed, both the husband and the wife must demonstrate virtuous behavior .

In one household, husbands often assume a dominant role for the majority of Chinese couples. The proverb "Men are in charge of the outside affairs, women are in charge of the inside affairs" can be used to describe a common phenomenon that has persisted in Chinese society for thousands of years. (Jingguang Li, 2018)That is to say, in addition to having to make enough money to sustain the entire family as the breadwinner, a husband also needs to deal with various other issues both within and particularly outside the home. As a result, from ancient times, the husband has taken on the role of the true head of the household and makes practically all of the decisions. Conversely, the wife is typically in charge of caring for the family, taking care of the husband, and conducting household chores. In traditional Chinese culture, a wife's role in a family is to always be that of an obedient one. She is not allowed to make crucial decisions for the family; instead, she must obey her husband. Additionally, the wife must respect her husband's face when participating in social activities, especially in front of his close friends or classmates, by speaking and acting appropriately.

Similarities

This paper explores the similarities and differences between husband and wife relationships and practices in Confucianism and Buddhism.

For a marriage to succeed, communication between spouses with different beliefs and view points is necessary. Husband and wife must share feelings and trust to prevent marital issues. As a result, it was said in Buddhist literature that husbands should refrain from mistreating, placing blame, or making their wives feel inferior in favor of practicing forgiveness and self-evaluation. Husbands should also abstain from infidelity. He ought to be devoted to and adore his wife. In addition to decorating his wife to look respectable and lovely, he ought to offer his wife the money he makes. The wife can both conserve and expedite the properties if she is wise and of good character. Additionally, they have to

evenly divide their properties with both sides' parents. Along with showing respect for one another, they should work together to find solutions to any issues that may arise. They should look out for one another when they are sick. When their friends are in need, they have to assist them. They ought to abide by these rules in order to maintain harmony between the husband and wife.

In a marriage, it's crucial to have mutual understanding, negotiate, spend time together, and show each other compassion and empathy. Additionally, Chinese spouses are typically eager to assist their wives with family and home affairs. This is a crucial component in maintaining a happy marriage. As a result, Confucian literature stressed the value of marriage in society.

It is said that after the formation of heaven and earth, the creation of men and women established relationships such as marriage, father-son, king-minister, superior-inferior, etc. before social rituals were created. This suggests that marriage is considered a long-lasting relationship that lasts throughout one's lifetime, amidst several other interpersonal relationships.

A husband and wife's affection for one another is akin to creating a harmonious melody. Husband and wife ought to treat one other with dignity and adopt a similar outlook. Additionally, there needs to be harmony in their relationships with one another. Wives typically live alone because they take care of the home and stay at home. To create a good married life, a husband needs to love his wife. In addition, they should strive to make their properties prosper by taking their parents' suggestions. These are the necessities for maintaining husband and wife harmony.

The aforementioned details demonstrate that the two literatures share similar viewpoints toward the husband and wife relationship.

Differences

In Buddhist literature, the guidance for husbands and wives to follow includes the wife knowing the husband's mind, looking after the parents-in-law as her parents, having good terms with the husband's relatives, and managing the finances given by her husband. It was found that because of the different attitudes and characters of husband and wife, a marriage can be broken.

Buddhist literature offers guidance to husbands and wives, advising them to understand each other's thoughts, treat each other's families with equal respect, and manage the money given by the husband. It also highlights that disagreements and differences in personality between partners can lead to a failed marriage.

In Confucian literature, it is mentioned that a woman has three obligations. Firstly, she must listen to her father's advice before marriage. Secondly, she must follow her husband's advice after marriage. Finally, she must listen to her sons' advice when she becomes a widow. Furthermore, the literature emphasizes three values- physical grace, faithfulness, polite discourse, dignity, and influence.

The practice of having secondary wives among Chinese people is generally caused by infertility or the husband's desire to have more sons so that the continuation of the family line can be assured. Therefore, unlike in Myanmar society, the necessity for a wife to have a son is emphasized in Chinese society. The above-mentioned factor indicates that two different ideologies have different principles to follow in a marriage.

In Chinese culture, infertile women and those whose husbands are unfaithful often seek the assistance of secondary wives. Consequently, having sons is regarded as a wife's duty. This issue highlights the differing beliefs regarding marriage between two opposing philosophies.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it's important to note that both spouses have a responsibility to build a strong marriage, and each must fulfill certain duties. By demonstrating morality, ethics, goodwill, and wisdom towards each other, a husband and wife can create a loving and peaceful family life. Despite the differences in their outward appearance, the examination of the husband-wife relationship from both Buddhist and Confucian perspectives reveals similar inner meanings.

The differences between the two are primarily due to cultural differences. Therefore, for the good of society, all cultures should uphold the values of their respective cultures. Further research is necessary to explore more interesting details of husband and wife relationship or other relationships for building a harmonious society.

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